

MODERN ASPECTS OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF OBSTRUCTIVE JAUNDICE

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Relevance. Among surgical diseases of the liver and extrahepatic bile ducts, the most severe are still those accompanied by persistent obstruction of the main bile ducts, leading to the development of obstructive jaundice. The diagnosis and treatment of patients with biliary hypertension syndrome due to obstructive jaundice (OJ) remains a pressing issue in emergency abdominal surgery.

Materials and Methods:

This study is based on the analysis of diagnostic results and staged decompression of the biliary tract using minimally invasive technologies in 226 patients with OJ of various origins from 2015 to 2022. The age of the patients ranged from 19 to 89 years. Of them, 117 (51.8%) were women and 109 (48.2%) were men. A total of 192 patients (84.6%) were admitted directly to the surgical department, while the remaining 34 (15.4%) were transferred from therapeutic and infectious disease units. For differential diagnosis of OJ, non-invasive methods were used: ultrasound (US), esophagogastroduodenoscopy (EGD), magnetic resonance cholangiopancreatography (MRCP), and multislice computed tomography (MSCT), as well as invasive methods: endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography (ERCP) and percutaneous transhepatic cholangiography (PTC).

Results:

The analysis showed that the criteria for determining the informativeness of the applied methods included the detection of stones, biliary strictures, masses, and dilation of intrahepatic bile ducts, common hepatic and bile ducts. Effective methods of eliminating biliary hypertension included various types of endoscopic decompression (n=57) and percutaneous transhepatic cholangiostomy (n=31), which were performed in combination with ERCP and PTC. A comparative evaluation of the feasibility of these decompression methods was conducted. Their effectiveness in resolving jaundice was 93.3%.

Conclusion:

The use of modern diagnostic methods (US, EGD, CT, MRCP) allows for a reliable confirmation of the mechanical nature of jaundice, identification of the cause

and level of obstruction, detection of tumor lesions in the area of the ampulla of Vater, and assessment of the extent of the pathological process. The choice of method and volume of intervention in cases of OJ depends primarily on the severity of jaundice, the general condition of the patient, the etiology of the disease, and the level and extent of the obstruction zone

